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**GREEN DIGITAL FINANCE: DRIVING SUSTAINABLE INVESTMENTS
THROUGH DECENTRALIZATION AND DIGITALIZATION**

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Abstract: This paper delves into the transformative potential of green digital finance at the intersection of decentralization and digitalization, driving sustainable investments and bolstering ecosystem resilience. It elucidates the paradigm shift brought about by decentralization in the financial landscape, emphasizing its role in restructuring institutional frameworks and diminishing the dominance of centralized authorities. Furthermore, it explores how decentralization within the digital financial realm fosters inclusivity and efficiency, paving the way for a more democratic financial system.

The integration of cutting-edge fintech tools, including artificial intelligence, machine learning, big data analytics, and blockchain, is highlighted as essential in enhancing the effectiveness of financial services and opening up new avenues for sustainable development initiatives. The article underscores the pivotal role of transparency, trust, and disintermediation in financial transactions, facilitated by blockchain technology's ability to provide transparent and immutable distributed ledger records accessible to all stakeholders. Additionally, it discusses the crucial

contribution of energy-efficient IoT technologies and eco-friendly solutions in curbing energy consumption and reducing carbon emissions.

Furthermore, the paper categorizes and elaborates on various types of sustainable digital finance solutions, ranging from green digital payment and account solutions to green digital asset solutions. Each category is exemplified by innovative fintech companies and platforms driving progress in sustainable finance. Lastly, the article underscores the significance of green regtech solutions in streamlining environmentally responsible reporting and ensuring compliance with sustainability regulations, thus fostering the development of a more resilient and efficient financial ecosystem.

In conclusion, the paper advocates for continued research and development in sustainable digital finance to advance green initiatives and address contemporary global challenges effectively.

Keywords: Financial ecosystem, Sustainable investments, decentralized finance (DeFi), Fintech, green digital finance (Green FinTech), greenwashing.

Introduction. In today's world, where sustainable development has become a priority, innovations in finance play a crucial role in ensuring sustainable investment. Achieving sustainable development goals requires proper implementation of environmental projects and increased financing through various green financing instruments. In 2023, approximately \$2.8 trillion was invested in the energy sector, with over \$1.7 trillion allocated to clean energy, including renewable energy sources [24]. However, addressing climate change and environmental issues requires much larger investments - between \$125 to \$275 trillion is needed by 2050 [12].

The financial system and financial technologies (FinTech) offer solutions for achieving sustainable development goals, including decentralized finance (DeFi), which ensures increased transparency, accountability, risk management, cost

reduction, and efficiency improvement. With the development of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), blockchain, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT), the tokenization of green assets has emerged as an opportunity to increase green financing volumes and achieve sustainable development goals.

Literature Review. In recent years, sustainable development and digitization have occupied a central place in scholarly discussions. The crucial role of the financial sector in transitioning to sustainable development is emphasized (Ibrahim R. L., 2022). Many studies have focused on the impact of green financing on the macro level and the consequences of implementing green financing (Shkodina I., Zelen'ko O., 2023). Representatives from both academia and practice, as well as regulatory institutions, have actively engaged in discussions. The European Union has adopted a Digital Finance Strategy, highlighting the need to study digital technologies in the financial sector and aiming to create a comprehensive regulatory framework that will facilitate the integration of distributed ledger technologies (DLT) and crypto-assets (European Commission (2023)). Additionally, the EU has developed an Action Plan on Sustainable Finance aimed at strengthening financing mechanisms supporting the transition to a sustainable economy European Commission (2023). However, a review of the scientific literature reveals a gap in the use of digital tools and fintech in sustainable projects.

This **article aims** to examine the use of digital finance and fintech in financing sustainable projects and elucidate trends in the development of sustainable digital finance. To achieve this goal, a combination of general scientific and specialized **research methods** was used: a systems approach to determine the transformation of the financial ecosystem under the influence of sustainable digital finance; analysis and synthesis to identify key trends and opportunities in the field of sustainable digital financing; expert assessment to develop approaches to improving the

institutionalization of sustainable finance and to confirm or complement the conclusions and proposals made in the article.

Main part. The concept of sustainable or green digital finance is the use of digital technologies, commonly known as fintech, to achieve certain ESG goals (ESG- environmental, social, governance - environment, social sphere, corporate governance). This concept emerged based on the principle that financial technologies can contribute to the advancement and development of environmentally friendly initiatives. Sustainable finance and digital finance have evolved independently for many years, but their integration into a unified concept of sustainable digital finance represents a new approach.

There is currently no universally accepted definition of sustainable digital finance. Considering that digital finance concerns the impact of the Internet and digital technologies on the financial sector (World Bank, 2016), and sustainable finance (GreenFi) entails the incorporation of environmental, social, and governance aspects into investment decisions (World Energy Investment, 2023), sustainable digital finance (Green FinTech) can be defined as the targeted application of digital finance to finance and support institutional and market mechanisms conducive to achieving sustainable development. The Green Digital Finance Alliance defines sustainable digital finance as technological innovations applied to any financial processes and products supporting sustainable development goals (Green Digital Finance Alliance, 2023).

Therefore, leveraging digital finance, including artificial intelligence (AI), big data, blockchain, and the Internet of Things (IoT), is both possible and necessary for achieving sustainable and inclusive economic growth. The emergence of these technologies has opened unprecedented opportunities for improving financial services overall and supporting green financing initiatives.

Analyzing the impact of sustainable digital finance on economic development requires identifying its types. The discussion often revolves around aligning with ESG criteria to denote certain activities, products, or services as environmentally friendly or sustainable. The main problem lies in the multitude of indicators that variously define, classify, assess, and measure ESG factors. This ambiguity creates significant obstacles for financial institutions and companies. Many entrepreneurs formally approach sustainable development reporting or merely apply sustainable development rhetoric (Johannes W.H. van der Waal, Thomas Thijssens, 2020). Consequently, the issue of greenwashing, which refers to deceptive tactics of companies falsely portraying their ESG commitments or exaggerating their environmental transition achievements, arises. This phenomenon is particularly significant in the context of financial technologies, where technology and finance convergence has facilitated the creation of new financial products oriented toward sustainability. For example, loans are provided to companies for sustainable development, but the funds are not actually used for such purposes; or fintech companies market their investment platform as environmentally friendly, yet the investments lack real environmental standards.

In 2023, the number of greenwashing cases among banks and financial services companies increased by 70% compared to the previous year. RepRisk, a company specializing in ESG research, documented 148 cases in the banking and financial services sector worldwide in 2023. Out of these, 106 cases were related to European financial institutions (Reuters, 2023). The banking and financial industries rank second only to the oil and gas sector in the number of greenwashing incidents. The growing number of greenwashing cases raises concerns as it affects trust in the financial industry, the reliability, and effectiveness of sustainable investments.

The current ambiguity surrounding ESG standards and methodology may lead some financial organizations to hesitate in investing in green projects, fearing

accusations of greenwashing. Regulators worldwide must focus on addressing this issue and implement measures to combat fraud. Defining various practices of greenwashing in financial technologies will not only improve understanding of the issue but also assist regulatory institutions and businesses in establishing an effective regulatory framework and industry standards to address this phenomenon. Financial sector institutions must collaborate with regulatory authorities and stakeholders to ensure transparency and accountability in ESG practices. Collaboration is crucial for creating a reliable foundation for assessing and verifying sustainability claims, aiding investors in making informed decisions.

The increasing number of incidents related to greenwashing is concerning, yet, on the other hand, they serve as a catalyst for change. The demand for sustainable financial projects will continue to grow, leading to further development of financial products across sectors that are linked to sustainability. In this context, the use of financial technologies to achieve sustainable development goals becomes paramount.

In the context of developing the digital ecosystem, decentralization of the financial system plays a pivotal role in transforming financial systems. According to the InsightAce Analytic report, the decentralized finance (DeFi) market revenue was estimated at \$20.22 billion in 2023 and is projected to reach \$398.77 billion by 2031 (CAGR 45.36% from 2023 to 2031) (InsightAce Analytic, 2024). Utilizing blockchain and distributed ledgers enables the creation of decentralized financial systems where transaction data is stored on various network nodes, eliminating the need for centralized financial institutions such as banks and other financial institutions. Distributed ledger technology provides unverified access to information and plays a leading role in ensuring transparency and immutability of all financial transactions. The blockchain market is growing rapidly. Experts estimate that it will reach \$99.37 billion in 2027 with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 55.0%. This is nearly ten times its value in 2022 (Research and Markets, 2022).

Considering that traditional cryptocurrency mining is energy-intensive (Bitcoin consumes over 125 TWh of electricity per year, exceeding the consumption level of many countries), green cryptocurrencies are gaining traction. Cryptocurrencies such as Chia, Iota (MIOTA), BitGreen (BITG), SolarCoin utilize energy-efficient methods to minimize environmental impact. A cryptocurrency becomes energy-efficient when its developers prioritize sustainability and work to reduce energy consumption and environmental impact (Medium, 2024).

The use of blockchain and asset tokenization proves to be powerful tools for creating digital assets representing green projects and making them accessible to a wide range of investors. Blockchain can divide company shares into smaller digital shares, convert them into tokens, and distribute them in a peer-to-peer transaction system (P2P). Thus, tokenization of green assets not only makes them accessible to investors but also promotes sustainable financing. And tokenizing traditional assets, such as government bonds, will instill trust in the crypto-financing system.

In the sphere of green investments, blockchain can be utilized to create a distributed ledger that records not only all financial transactions but also other aspects of environmental projects. Each transaction can be tracked from the investor's wallet to the specific financial project in real-time. The Islamic Development Bank (Saudi Arabia) uses blockchain for instant clearing and settlement of transactions. In such conditions, it is possible not only to efficiently track the movement of funds but also to confirm the real impact of investments on sustainable development. For example, FeverTokens utilizes blockchain for monitoring and supervision throughout the entire lifecycle of tokenized green bonds (Bank for International Settlements, 2023). Additionally, in November 2023, Societe Generale issued its first digital green bond as a security token registered on SG-FORGE on the public Ethereum blockchain with the ability to track ESG data (Societe Generale – FORGE, 2023). Essentially, this became the first step in using blockchain as a data repository and certification tool for

issuers and investors to support ESG. This increases transparency in investment processes, makes operations less susceptible to manipulation, reduces costs for users, and enhances trust between investors and companies.

Analysis of sources suggests that in order to enhance the concept of tokenization in the sustainable investment market, the following aspects should be considered:

- simplify the tokenization process by developing intuitive and user-friendly interfaces for users and reducing technical barriers for investors and companies intending to tokenize their assets;
- expand the scope of application. Explore tokenization opportunities in various sectors, including real estate, intellectual property, etc., and broaden the concept of tokenization to new types of assets to increase scalability and diversity;
- develop clear legislation, standards, and regulations for tokenization to ensure compliance and investor protection;
- improve the technical aspects of tokenization to ensure a high level of security against cyber threats and fraud;
- create ecosystems that integrate various technological solutions for tokenization with other technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, and distributed ledgers;
- develop industry standards and joint initiatives to support sustainable and transparent development of the tokenization market.

An important element in the modern decentralized financial ecosystem is the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML). By analyzing market trends, geopolitical events, technological progress, and other factors, AI algorithms can predict possible risks and suggest optimal management strategies. AI gathers and analyzes unstructured data from the internet, including expert reports, media mentions, social media sentiments, company disclosures, and other data, and offers

investors portfolios based on personalized preferences, ESG ratings, and green assets (Elouidani R., Outouzzalt A., 2023). For example, MistEO utilizes the power of AI and data analytics about weather conditions to provide farmers with crop analytics, minimizing the risk of financial losses (Bank for International Settlements, 2023).

In 2023, the global AI market was estimated at \$200 bil. According to Next Move Strategy Consulting, it is expected that the AI market will grow to nearly two trillion \$ dollars by 2030 (Next Move Strategy Consulting, 2023).

Source: Next Move Strategy Consulting

Figure 1. Global artificial intelligence (AI) market size 2021 - 2023, forecast to 2030 (\$ bil)

According to the United Nations Environment Programmer (UNEP), by 2030, AI could increase the global GDP by \$15-20 trillion. Ensuring ecological and social resilience of the GDP can be achieved through the digitization of green finance.

The significant increase in energy consumption, driven by Internet of Things (IoT) technology, has created new challenges for creating a more ecological ecosystem. In 2023, the number of connected IoT devices grew to approximately 16.7 billion (Alsharif Mohammed H., 2023). Starting from January 1, 2024, all major corporations are required to report various IoT data, including pollution levels, greenhouse gas emissions, water consumption, and energy usage (according to European Sustainability Reporting Standards, ESRS).

Green IoT is a new area that has attracted significant attention from researchers and industries, as it provides energy-efficient services and enables the production and use of renewable energy. IoT-enabled devices can track and optimize energy consumption in real-time, leading to waste reduction and carbon emission reduction. IoT contributes to smart transportation systems, which optimize traffic flow, reduce congestion, and minimize fuel consumption.

Thus, the decentralization of the financial system entails a change in its institutional structure and a reduction in the role of centralized institutions. Decentralizing the digital financial ecosystem helps create a democratic and efficient financial system for all its participants by:

- implementing fintech: AI, ML, big data analytics, blockchain, and other technologies enhance the efficiency of financial services and provide new opportunities for sustainable development;
- transparency and trust: Blockchain records everything in a distributed ledger, making it accessible and traceable for all ecosystem participants;
- absence (or reduction) of intermediaries in financial transactions and cost reduction. The absence of intermediaries reduces service costs and commissions, the total costs of participants in financial transactions and information asymmetry;
- effective risk management: Implementing distributed ledgers allows for risk management mechanisms and control over financial transactions, enhancing security and reducing fraud opportunities;
- global access: A decentralized financial ecosystem enables the provision of financial services globally, regardless of users' geographic location;
- inclusivity: The digital ecosystem can serve populations previously excluded due to geographic, economic, or social constraints;
- the ecosystem promotes the development of sustainable finance as investors can choose green investments and support environmentally responsible projects.

In the development of a decentralized digital financial ecosystem, an important factor is the definition of various types of sustainable digital finance. Initially, they largely mirrored established segments of financial products, supplemented with digital data and channels. However, today, due to the expansion of fintech categories in various taxonomies, types of sustainable digital finance are defined by fintech solutions designed to better align the financial system's behavior with environmental goals. Considering this, the elements of sustainable digital finance can be defined as follows (Green Digital Finance Alliance, 2023):

- green digital payment and account solutions. Payment platforms that integrate green functionalities as part of the payment experience. Example: Paygreen - a Swiss fintech company that offers a payment system through which consumers can obtain the carbon footprint of the online store where they made a purchase;

- sustainable digital investment solutions. Digital platforms that offer automated green financial planning and investment services. For instance, FNZ Impact, a global capital management platform, provides automated and tailored sustainable solutions, including ESG report aggregation and conversion of savings into sustainable investments based on user preferences;

- digital ESG-data and analytics solutions. Digital tools that provide investors with automated ESG company ratings, green asset ratings, carbon accounting, automated credit assessment, and more. For example, Satelligence, a Dutch fintech, specializes in providing high-resolution satellite data to financial institutions for monitoring deforestation risks;

- sustainable digital crowdfunding. Platforms that raise capital in small increments from a large number of individuals or entities to fund environmentally friendly businesses and projects. Bettervest, a German crowdfunding platform, raises capital for the energy transition by allowing people to collectively invest small sums of money in renewable energy and energy efficiency projects;

- green digital risk analysis and insurtech solutions. Software and platforms leveraging AI and IoT to optimize the environmental friendliness of insurance products and minimize risks associated with climate and nature. For instance, Jupiter, an American fintech, provides climate analyses of physical risks to organizations affected by climate change;

- sustainable digital deposit and lending solutions. Digital loans for financing projects or loans linked to environmentally friendly behavior. Pensumo, a Spanish fintech, offers a pension program for users adhering to environmentally friendly consumption behavior and collaborating with retailers committed to sustainable development;

- eco-friendly digital asset solutions. Tokens and cryptocurrencies with environmental properties and blockchain infrastructure designed for sustainable use. Treecoin, a Swiss fintech, sells tokens tied to real eucalyptus trees, with each sold tree generating 100 tokens distributed among owners to support sustainable development through land acquisition and seedlings for eucalyptus cultivation in Paraguay;

- green regtech solutions. Technology utilized for environmentally responsible reporting, automated assessment of financial products and services based on environmental standards and taxonomy. For instance, Greenomy, a Belgian fintech, assists corporations in complying with EU legislation on sustainable financing by digitizing data collection and reporting processes, facilitating preparation of reports on the EU taxonomy, the EU Regulation on disclosure of sustainable finance (SFDR), and the EU Directive on reporting on sustainable development (CSRD).

In conclusion, the sustainability and efficiency of the financial system are becoming increasingly important in the context of today's global challenges. The decentralization of the financial system combined with digital technologies plays a key role in implementing green investments and improving ecosystem resilience. One

of the key conclusions is that sustainable digital finance can be a crucial tool in supporting green initiatives and achieving sustainable development goals. The use of modern digital technologies in the financial sector will enhance the efficiency of financial services and support projects aimed at environmental preservation and positive social change. It is also important to define the role of digital finance in the need for standardization and consistency of ESG criteria to avoid greenwashing and ensure credible sustainable development information.

The concept of sustainable digital finance opens up new opportunities for sustainable investing, as its use increases transparency and the ability to identify and minimize risks, reduces information asymmetry and costs, and enables the provision of financial services regardless of geographical, economic, or social constraints. Further research in this direction will contribute to the creation of a more efficient and sustainable financial system that responds to the growing challenges of the present day.

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